

NOTES

Colorimetric Estimation and Photometric Titration of Sodium Thiosulphate Using Cacotheline as Reagent

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CACOTHELIN of unspecified purity has often been used as a redox indicator and for the detection and colorimetric determination of tin(II), iron(II) and vanadium(III)¹⁻³. The preparation of highly pure cacotheline and its use as an oxidimetric reagent has been reported^{4,5}. The pure sample was used as a reagent by Murty and Rao⁶ for the detection of thiosulphate. This pure reagent has now been studied for photometric titration and colorimetric estimation of thiosulphate.

Experimental

Cacotheline solution (0.005 M) in 0.02 M HCl was prepared and standardised iodometrically and used after suitable dilution. A Shimadzu double beam spectrophotometer (UV 140.02) and a Klett-Summerson photoelectric colorimeter with a green filter (maximum transmission 500-560 m μ) were used. The photoelectric colorimeter was equipped with 15 cm optical cells.

Colorimetric estimation :

In each 50 ml volumetric flask 1-4 ml cacotheline solution, depending on the amount of sodium thiosulphate present, and 20 ml 10 N hydrochloric acid or 27.5 ml 15 N sulphuric acid are taken. Different volumes of sodium thiosulphate are added in different flasks and the contents are made upto the mark. Cacotheline equivalent to the sodium thiosulphate is reduced to pink coloured product. The reduction of cacotheline to the pink coloured reduced product takes place immediately and the colour is stable for about 30 min at room temp. The optical density of each solution is measured and the amount calculated.

Photometric titration :

5 ml 10 N hydrochloric acid or 6.5 ml 15 N sulphuric acid is taken in a 15 ml capacity optical cell of the Klett-Summerson photoelectric colorimeter and a stream of carbondioxide is passed through the contents for about 10 min to drive off dissolved

oxygen. Then 0.5-2.0 ml cacotheline solution is added and the total volume is made to 10 ml. This mixture is then titrated with sodium thiosulphate. Passage of carbondioxide is continued throughout the titration except while taking the reading of absorbance. Usual volume correction is applied for plotting the titration curves.

Results and Discussion

The absorption spectra of the product obtained by the reduction of cacotheline with sodium thiosulphate at the recommended acidities showed a maximum at 530 m μ . One mole of cacotheline reacted with one mole of sodium thiosulphate for its reduction to the pink product. The reaction mechanism has already been discussed⁵. Beer's law is obeyed in the range of 2.0-20 mg sodium thiosulphate. The minimum amount of sodium thiosulphate that can be estimated using this procedure is found to be 2 mg in 50 ml solution. The results of the photometric titration and colorimetric estimation are given in Table 1. The standard deviation is found to be 0.015.

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF SODIUM THIOSULPHATE

Photometric titration method Sodium thiosulphate (mg)			Colorimetric estimation method Sodium thiosulphate (mg)		
Taken	Found	% error	Taken	Found	% error
2.562	2.550	0.47	2.512	2.501	0.44
5.120	5.098	0.43	5.024	5.002	0.44
10.18	10.14	0.39	10.05	10.00	0.50
15.24	15.19	0.33	15.07	15.01	0.40
19.83	19.79	0.20	18.84	18.79	0.27

An advantage of cacotheline is that the reagent keeps its titre unaltered even after 15 days if prepared in 0.02 M hydrochloric acid and kept in an amber coloured bottle.

Effect of diverse ions :

In the determination of sodium thiosulphate employing cacotheline as reagent antimony(V), vanadium(V), molybdenum(VI), tungsten(VI), cerium(IV), uranium(VI), chloride, bromide, iron(II), hydrazine and mercury(I) do not interfere. Tin(II), titanium(III) and vanadium(II) interfere at all concentrations.

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Amperometric Determination of Manganese(II) with 2-Hydroxy-1-Acetonaphthoneoxime*

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THERE is a paucity of literature on the amperometric determination of manganese(II), particularly using oximes as titrants. During a detailed investigation on the utility of 2-hydroxy-1-acetonaphthoneoxime (2-HANO) and its isomer, 1-hydroxy-2-acetonaphthoneoxime (1-HANO)¹ as analytical reagents, it was observed that both the reagents give dark green precipitates with Mn(II) at pH 8.0-8.5. These reactions were utilised for the amperometric determination of Mn(II) in view of the favourable polarographic behaviour of Mn(II). The results of investigations on the use of 2-HANO as an amperometric titrant for Mn(II) are presented here. The reagent has already been used for gravimetric^{2,3} and amperometric⁴ determination of copper, nickel and palladium.

Experimental

2-Hydroxy-1-acetonaphthoneoxime was prepared⁵, recrystallised from rectified spirit and vacuum dried. A standard solution (0.025 M) was prepared in rectified spirit. A stock solution of manganese sulphate was also prepared and standardised⁶. The apparatus used for the amperometric titration was the same as described earlier⁶.

The polarographic behaviour of Mn(II) was studied at d.m.e. in presence of NH₄Cl-NH₄OH buffer of pH 8.0-8.5. The reagent did not give a reduction wave in ammoniacal medium. Hence the amperometric determination of Mn(II) was carried out at an applied potential of -1.7 V (vs SCE).

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Procedure :

To the aliquots of standard manganese sulphate solution (0.99-9.52 mg Mn) were added 20 ml ammonium chloride (1 M), 5 ml ammonium hydroxide (1 M), 2 ml Triton —X— 100 solution and 5 ml rectified spirit and the total volume made up to 80 ml with distilled water. The solution was deaerated by passing a stream of pure hydrogen for 15 min and then titrated with a standard solution of the reagent running down from a 5-ml microburette. The current readings were noted at an applied potential of -1.7 V (vs SCE) after each addition of the reagent followed by deaeration. A plot of current readings corrected for volume changes against the volume of titrant gave an L-shaped curve. Manganese (0.99-9.52 mg) could thus be determined with an average error of $\pm 0.43\%$. Six determinations of 1.972 mg manganese gave a standard deviation of 0.006₄ mg and a relative mean error of $\pm 0.05\%$.

In the case of lower amounts of manganese, higher values were obtained as the concentration of ammonia and alcohol were increased, which might have been due to the solubility of the manganese complex formed.

Studies of Interferences :

Copper, palladium and zinc did not interfere, as they did not give any precipitate under the experimental conditions. The interferences due to iron(III) and aluminium(III) could be prevented by the addition of sodium fluoride solution (0.5 M). Cobalt(II) was masked by ammonium thiocyanate solution (0.5 M). Masking nickel by cyanide was of no use. Hence, a prior separation of nickel from manganese was considered essential.

Determination of copper and manganese from the same solution :

The reactivity of the reagent with two metals under different experimental conditions such as applied potential and pH of quantitative precipitation facilitates their determination from binary mixtures without separation. This principle was used for the determination of copper and nickel from the same solution by many workers^{4,6-8}. The same was extended for the determination of copper and manganese from the same solution. Aliquots of standard solutions of copper sulphate and manganese sulphate were taken in the wider limb of the H-cell. A dilute solution of sodium hydroxide (1 M) was added dropwise until a slight but permanent precipitate of the hydroxides of the metals was obtained. The precipitate was just dissolved by the addition of HCl (1 M). To this were added 25 ml ammonium chloride solution (1 M), 2 ml Triton —X— 100 solution and 5 ml rectified spirit and the total volume made up to 80 ml. Addition of ammonium chloride was preferred to an acetate buffer (pH 4.0-4.5) to avoid addition of large amounts of ammonia required to raise the pH in the subsequent determination of manganese. Copper was determined at an applied potential of -0.4 V (vs SCE).